

The appropriacy of an imported English language textbook: Malaysian teachers' experiences

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The adoption of the Common European Framework of References (CEFR) in the national educational blueprint has changed the overall landscape of English language education in Malaysia. After the alignment of the national English language curriculum in 2017, all locally published English language textbooks were taken over by imported ones, resulting in huge debates among the stakeholders in the country. This study examined teachers' evaluations of two essential elements of a CEFR-aligned English language textbook—authenticity and intercultural competence—by adopting a mixed-method approach using a survey of 450 respondents and semi-structured interviews with 10 participants. Taking the *Super Minds* textbook as a subject, teacher participants rated the two elements as “moderate,” where they found that the imported textbook hardly accommodates learners from lower socioeconomic status. The absence of local cultural representations could worsen the learning process as teachers have to adapt almost all contents in the textbook to meet their learners' profiles.

Keywords: Authenticity; CEFR; Imported Textbooks; Interculturality

1. Introduction

English language textbooks undeniably play a significant role in English language teaching (ELT) as they present standard cultural and linguistic inputs to language learners and serve as a medium for transmitting social ideologies and legitimating social practices (Apple & Beyer, 1983; Canale, 2016). The use of an ideal textbook in an English as a Second Language (ESL) context could positively affect learners' outcomes (Mostafa & Jahan, 2024) and take charge of the learning process, albeit with non-existing or bad teaching (Ahmed, 2017). Theorists and practitioners, however, have raised an issue with language learning materials that merely emphasize the target language to the extent that learners' “interests, wants, and talents” (Tomlinson & Masuhara,

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2018, p. 37) are neglected. Therefore, any prescribed textbook should simultaneously have (a) a balance in considering learners' needs (cf. Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Pirmoradian et al., 2024; Salmani Nodoushan, 2006, 2007, 2020) and (b) appropriate content in facilitating learners' mastery of the language.

The trend of the use of English language textbooks in ESL and EFL contexts has changed remarkably over the last decades, from monocultural content focusing on native-speaking countries to multi- and inter-cultural content developed by local authors (Rahim & Daghigh, 2020). However, due to the adoption of the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), which is believed to be able to internationalize local English language curricula (cf. Mirdehghan Farashah, 2021; Mostafa & Jahan, 2024), the Malaysian government has decided to import all English language textbooks for primary and secondary schools. The framework, as claimed by the Ministry of Education (MoE) Malaysia, is in favor of students and teachers being proficient in the English language, which involves curriculum, assessment, and teaching and learning (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2015). The use of imported textbooks is seen as a requirement for aligning the curriculum with the CEFR, which local authors are assumed to lack experience with (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2015).

Such an action has received various feedback from the stakeholders. Some experts opined that foreign elements in English language textbooks would benefit students, such as exposing learners to other cultures, which can later be used in local and foreign contexts (Sani, 2018). Nonetheless, local studies have shown contradiction to the statement, arguing that imported textbooks are unfavorable to the cultural representations (see Ahamat & Kabilan, 2022; Daghigh & Rahim, 2020; Rahim & Daghigh, 2020). Ahamat and Kabilan (2022), for instance, found that teachers have problems delivering foreign cultural contexts and practices to students at rural schools. Meanwhile, Daghigh and Rahim (2020) revealed that currently-in-use imported textbooks contain neoliberal values that may encourage learners to adjust their attitudes and behaviors according to the foreign values presented in the books. In another study, it was reported that the locally-developed textbooks used before the implementation of the CEFR presented wider intercultural content and met the objectives of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) better than the imported books (Rahim & Daghigh, 2020). Hence, importing all English language textbooks from international publishers may not be in the country's best interest because the CEFR is not context-specific, yet providing leeway for users to adapt the framework to their specific context.

The above-mentioned problems with the imported textbooks, nonetheless, are not specific to the textbook under investigation in this study, the *Super Minds*

textbook. For that matter, it is important to examine the elements of authenticity and intercultural competence (IC) presented in the book, as they are interconnected and able to affect learners in many ways. Studies have proven that authentic materials are an effective tool in bringing context into language teaching (Shrum & Glisan, 2000), a motivating factor in learning a target language (Albiladi, 2019; Zohoorian, 2015), and a source of engagement in a language classroom (Din & Yamat, 2020; Sánchez, 2018). According to Zohoorian (2015), other aspects, like learners' interests, goals, needs, and age, must be considered when creating authentic learning situations besides integrating learners' past and new knowledge. The use of authentic materials allows learners to explore different cultural norms, beliefs, values, and practices that will assist them in intercultural communication. However, considering that the English language is now treated more as a global language, the cultural representations in a textbook should concentrate not only on the inner circle but also on the outer and expanding circles of the English language. In fact, within a local setting (in this case, Malaysia), cultural values and practices are diverse as the country consists of multicultural societies.

The *Super Minds* textbook was particularly chosen in this study because it is the first imported textbook used in Malaysia and has been used by Year One and Year Two students of primary schools since the first year of the CEFR implementation in 2017. Since its official use in 2017, there has been no further evaluation of the book's appropriacy, though there was a study on challenges faced by English language teachers in using the textbook in their respective classrooms (Din & Yamat, 2020).

The textbook, which is internationally published, adopts Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) (Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 2024; Martín Del Pozo, 2017; Puchta et al., 2012), allowing learners to learn a language through new subject contents. Though CLIL has been claimed as an approach that can improve intercultural competencies and communicative abilities (Salmani Nodoushan, 2020; Vu & Nguyen, 2022), its implications for young learners still need to be explored. Textbook evaluation, particularly from teachers' perspectives, is substantial for uncovering the 'affordances', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021), and inadequacies of particular materials used, as they are the implementers of the newly introduced CEFR policy in the English language education setting and the main witnesses of problems at school level. This study, therefore, comes with two objectives: (a) to examine how Malaysian teachers perceive the extent to which the *Super Minds* textbook is appropriate for learners in terms of its authenticity in the local context, and (b) to explore whether or not Malaysian teachers consider that the *Super Minds* textbook can prepare learners for ICC.

2. Background

2.1. Authenticity

In language learning, scholars in materials development have presented diverse ideas regarding authenticity. For instance, McDonough and Shaw (2003) define authenticity as “an approximation as possible to the world outside the classroom, in the selection of both language materials and of the activities and method used for practice in the classroom” (p. 40). Meanwhile MacDonald et al. (2006) propose four categories of authenticity which include (a) text authenticity, (b) competence authenticity, (c) learner authenticity, and (d) classroom authenticity. This study deals with the prescribed materials in the classroom, with a focus on text authenticity, which MacDonald et al. (2006) define as “a correspondence between ‘pedagogic’ language, text or material[s], and ‘real world’ language, texts or artifacts” (p. 25). It is therefore assumed that the materials used in English language classrooms could include real-situation images and illustrations in the teaching content so that learners can make connections between what they learn and their real-life practices.

In this study, the term authenticity is extended to the wider concept, which is not only limited to learners’ teaching and learning contexts but also includes any elements that can accommodate the teaching and learning process, as proposed by Mukundan et al. (2011). In this case, the general attributes of the textbook—e.g., using effective texts and visuals, addressing learners’ language ability, and complementing with suitable materials (supplemented materials)—were also included. Previous studies are not only in support of having authentic materials as an effective tool in bringing context into language teaching (Shrum & Glisan, 2000), but they also work as a motivating factor among learners to learn a target language (Albiladi, 2019; Zohoorian, 2015) and a source of engagement in a language classroom (Din & Yamat, 2020; Sánchez, 2018). Even though the *Super Minds* textbook is claimed to be CEFR-aligned with communicative competency objectives (Chin & Rajaendram, 2017), it is important to evaluate the book’s authenticity from local teachers’ points of view because different contexts of teaching (e.g., urban, rural, and remote schools) may have different perspectives on the element of authenticity in the book.

2.2. Intercultural competence

Globalization and multiculturalism have caused “geopolitical and societal shifts” (Zhang & Zhou, 2019, p. 31) and led people worldwide to live together in a culturally diverse society. As a result, intercultural competence (IC) has been conceived as an “indicator of interculturalism” (Zhang & Zhou, 2019, p. 31); it has been used in many official documents aiming to nurture all-round citizens. Byram and Masuhara (2013) classify IC into the dimensions of (a)

knowledge, (b) awareness, (c) attitudes, and (d) skills. These dimensions equally acknowledge the culture of self and others, where learners should be able to appreciate foreign cultures and, most importantly, cultures that construct their society within their inner circle. The main issue with IC is that IC theories are predominantly Eurocentric, focusing on European and Western cultures, resulting in “a challenge to the application of Eurocentric theories in other cultural settings” (Dalib et al., 2017, p. 1). Consequently, learners tend to look outward to foreign cultures rather than balancing between the two, foreign and local, in the name of intercultural competence.

As Malaysia is multicultural and consists of a multi-ethnic community with more than one linguistic ability, there is a need to revisit the idea of IC in the Malaysian setting. This reconceptualization provides micro perspectives on viewing communication specific to the local context rather than viewing IC solely from a Eurocentric perspective. The idea of IC can even be interpreted locally in the development of ELT materials as the English language is now extensively used in many former British and American colonies and is also treated as a lingua franca all over the world (Chaka, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Nkhi & Shange, 2024; Xu & Fang, 2024). The notion of English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) can be associated with the ‘post-colonial’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024) framework that perceives ELF as a medium of intercultural communication. The growth of ELF has changed the purpose of learning the English language from obtaining native-like English to mastering the language for international communication. Therefore, blending local cultures and other foreign cultures to bridge the “world of English” (Rahim, 2018, p. 3) is necessary as learners can use those acquired cultural elements for international communication.

2.3. Textbook evaluation

There are three types of materials evaluation proposed in the literature (Cunningsworth, 1995; Ellis, 1997): (a) pre-use evaluation, (b) in-use evaluation, and (c) post-use evaluation. The first type of evaluation is meant to examine the potential performance of a textbook and is typically used in selecting the most suitable book for learners. In contrast, the second type of evaluation is designed to explore the materials presently being used, which helps teachers explore the weaknesses or strengths of the book while using it. Meanwhile, the last type refers to the evaluation of the materials used in a particular learning situation that also reflects the quality of the book. These types of evaluation may play different roles depending on the purpose of the evaluation; however, they generally enable the stakeholders to discriminate against textbooks that are inappropriate for their students (Mohammadi & Abdi, 2014) and opt for suitable books that meet students’ needs and teachers’ pedagogical values.

As Malaysia is now adopting global textbooks produced by international publishers to support the CEFR practices in the English language curriculum (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2015), textbook evaluation is even more crucial to the measurement of effectiveness of the textbook in supporting the curriculum reforms. The currently in-use imported books have been criticized for many reasons including (a) imbalance of cultural content (Din & Yamat, 2020; Rahim & Daghigh, 2020; Takal et al., 2021) and (b) high lexical density (Takal et al., 2021). However, that is not the case in Toprakci and Özeydinli's (2021) finding, where Turkish teachers were found to favor textbooks with "less localized content" (p. 854) for more effective English language teaching. Therefore, a textbook evaluation is crucial in determining teachers' attitudes toward the textbook used in the classroom since different teaching contexts may have other preferences over teaching materials. The textbook evaluation involving teachers appears in line with what Littlejohn (2011, p. 180) has put forward:

We need, therefore, a means to examine the implications that use of a set of materials may have for classroom work and thus come to grounded opinions about whether or not the methodology and content of the materials is appropriate for a particular teaching context.

3. Method

This study aimed to examine how Malaysian teachers perceive the appropriateness of the *Super Minds* textbook concerning its authenticity and its potential to prepare local learners for IC. A mixed-methods research design was, therefore, adopted using an explanatory approach, which involved the collection of quantitative data first, and then a qualitative method was used to provide a detailed explanation of the existing data. This method is commonly used, as one type of data collection was able to offset "potential limitations or lack of depth" (Egeberg et al., 2020, p. 111) of the other type of data collection.

3.1. Instruments

Referring to the research questions, two research instruments were employed to collect the data: (a) a questionnaire, and (b) an interview guide.

The questionnaire was developed based on Mukundan et al.'s (2011) textbook evaluation criteria, MacDonald et al.'s (2006) authenticity, Byram and Masuhara's (2013) criteria for intercultural education material evaluation, and Dervin's (2016) interculturality. It contains 83 questions, consisting of 79 closed-ended questions and four open-ended questions, specifying the two main variables under investigations—i.e., authenticity, and IC elements of the textbook. The attribute of authenticity is classified into general attributes and

teaching and learning content covering listening, speaking, reading, writing, vocabulary, and grammar. Meanwhile, the element of IC stands on its own because it was advised by the experts in the validation process that only criteria involving knowledge, awareness, and attitudes should be included for lower primary school level evaluation, whereas skills can be evaluated when the learners can transfer all of the required skills into actual practice in intercultural communication. The three criteria under IC consist of some overlapping constructs, especially concerning knowledge and attitudes; therefore, all of the items are grouped together under one dimension. The proportion of the items between authenticity and IC is imbalanced because the elements of authenticity are elicited through language skills and components specified in the textbook.

The questionnaire was validated by three experts in the textbook evaluation and English language curriculum. Prior to data collection, a pilot study was conducted with 30 teachers of similar characteristics to the target teacher respondents. Afterwards, Cronbach's *alpha* values for all of the dimensions were estimated, and the results showed that they ranged from .910 to .971, which is considered "strong" (.91 to .93) and "excellent" (.93 to .94) (Taber, 2018, p. 1278).

Meanwhile, the interview questions were validated by a qualitative research expert to ensure that the included questions were in line with the research objectives. The questions in the semi-structured interview identify teachers' experiences using the *Super Minds* textbook, the challenges, and their perceptions of the elements of authenticity and IC imposed in the book. These questions were considered important to understand the real problems and get genuine responses from the grassroots level. They also work for data triangulation, enabling the researchers to delve into the problems that teachers encounter.

3.2. Participants

This study employed convenience sampling for the survey and purposive sampling for the semi-structured interviews. The survey questionnaire was distributed to English language teachers teaching Year One and Year Two students. The reason behind the selection was to obtain rich data regarding school teachers' experiences dealing with the *Super Minds* textbook with their students at their respective schools. The questionnaire was successfully completed by 450 English language teachers, and semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 English language teachers from different school localities—i.e., urban, rural, and remote. The number of interview participants was based on the researchers' accessibility and the participants' willingness to

participate in the study. Table 1 and Table 2 present the demographic profiles of the respondents for the survey and the interview respectively.

Table 1
The Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	84	18.7
	Female	366	81.3
School Locality	Urban	125	27.8
	Rural or Indigenous	308	68.4
	Remote	17	3.8

Table 2
The Demographic Profile of Interviewed Participants

Participant (P)	Gender	School Locality
P1	Male	Rural
P2	Male	Remote
P3	Male	Rural*
P4	Male	Remote
P5	Male	Rural*
P6	Female	Urban
P7	Female	Urban
P8	Female	Urban
P9	Female	Urban
P10	Female	Urban

*Indigenous school

3.3. Data collection and analysis

The data were collected through online platforms using Google Forms, where the link to the survey was posted on *WhatsApp*, *Facebook*, and *Twitter*. To reach a bigger size of sample, State and District Education Offices also assisted in reaching out to potential respondents in their respective districts. Overall, the data collection process took place for a month. Upon securing the data, the close-ended responses were quantitatively analyzed using the *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)*. Descriptive analysis was carried out on the close-ended responses to obtain the mean scores of teachers' evaluation of the elements of authenticity and IC in the textbook. Meanwhile, the interview recordings were manually transcribed and deductively coded following the two coding schemes (i.e., authenticity, and IC) to support the findings obtained from the quantitative data. The data coding was validated by the second author, and some significant data extracts were presented in the findings section.

4. Results

Quantitatively, the mean scores from the findings were interpreted into three categories: low (1.00-2.33), moderate (2.34-3.67), and high (3.68-5.00). These numerical data were supported by the semi-structured interview responses.

4.1. Authenticity

This study extends the definition of authenticity to a broader dimension, including the general attributes of the textbook and all of the language skills integrated into the book. Table 3 presents the mean score of the overall evaluation of the authenticity of the *Super Minds* textbook.

Table 3

The Mean Scores of the Authenticity Elements of the Super Minds Textbook

	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
General attributes	1.07	5.00	3.47	.86
Speaking	1.00	5.00	3.30	.93
Listening	1.00	5.00	3.35	.88
Reading	1.00	5.00	3.35	.90
Writing	1.00	5.00	3.34	.92
Vocabulary	1.00	5.00	3.49	.93
Grammar	1.00	5.00	3.36	.94
Overall Authenticity	1.01	5.00	3.38	.84

Based on Table 3, all elements including the overall element of authenticity obtained a “moderate” mean score. This mixed perception towards authenticity may imply that teachers were neither in full agreement nor disagreement that the book presents authentic content to their respective learners. General attributes and vocabulary obtained the highest mean scores, whereas speaking gained the lowest mean score in the evaluation.

Varied responses about authenticity emerged from the qualitative data, particularly referring to school categories—urban, rural, and remote. However, all seem to raise the need for using more materials related to students' real lives. Language content should be modified in such a way as to match students' proficiency as well as learning conditions. Modified language content was what the teachers seemed to expect. The following excerpt exhibits the inauthentic language and content used in the current textbook:

... the term “trainers” is used to refer to “sports shoes” (commonly used in Malaysia). I must always remind my students that this book is from the UK, so the words used are commonly used in the country. The book also covers about Halloween. Since it's there, teachers have to do some

research to explain to learners about the celebration or anything unfamiliar to them. (P6)

Teachers' creativity and competence mattered in this case, as there was a unique response from P10 that very often she just took the language content from the textbook to teach but made use of what was available to clarify meanings.

. . . in terms of the content, I believe it can be localized yet aligned with CEFR. For example, when I teach the set of foods and fruits, there's this one particular module, I don't think it will bring harm I switch the fruits to something that students have always seen, even the layout of the market presented in the book, something that they can immediately relate to. (P10)

However, there were also concerns reported by some of the participants from remote and rural schools that the imported textbook does not accommodate teaching and learning since the book has to be adapted most of the time.

I'm aware that we can adapt the content to local food to replace all the foreign items in the *Super Minds*, but in this case, there's no point in using the book if teachers have to adapt or change the content completely. (P5)

In fact, P3 and P5, who teach at indigenous schools, could barely use the book in their respective classrooms. P3 also pointed out that the excessive foreignness in the textbook may not only further demotivate his learners in their learning of the language but also inculcate "white supremacy" among local teachers and learners. According to P3, while English language textbooks can be locally developed, the county opted for imported ones as they are believed to have better quality and are of international standard.

Nonetheless, almost all of the participants agreed that the *Super Minds* textbook provides teaching convenience, and it is complemented with a workbook. The workbook contains numerous activities that cover all of the language skills and skill components. Such an attribute could not be found in the previously-used locally-developed textbook as teachers had to construct their own activities based on lessons in that textbook. Despite such a privilege, learners had problems with 'inauthentic' activities such as strong accents in listening activities and unrealistic instances that learners were unable to relate to in their daily practices.

Overall, it can be summarized that teachers in rural and remote schools are the most affected by imported textbooks (in this case, *Super Minds*) as the content does not represent local students' real-life situations. Their attitudes towards

the authenticity of the book differed according to learners' locality due to different exposure to the language. Unlike those in remote and rural areas, teachers at urban schools were bound by less or no adaptation to the materials because their students could already make sense of the textbook content.

4.2. IC element

Table 4 presents the mean score for the element of IC presented in the *Super Minds* textbook.

Table 4

The Overall Mean Score of the IC Element of the Super Minds Textbook

	Min	Max	M	SD
Overall Intercultural Competence (IC)	1.00	5.00	3.22	.82

The IC section of the questionnaire, which consisted of 14 items, was also rated as "moderate" by the respondents. The moderate response suggests room for improvement in introducing the elements of IC to young learners.

Qualitatively, all teacher participants in Malaysia highlighted interculturality in the broader sense. Interview participants called for integrating local cultures into the English language textbook. According to them, Malaysia is of multiple races and ethnicities, which can become an initial step in introducing learners to multiculturalism and a source for developing IC. The following are excerpts from the interviews representing participants' ideas of integrating local cultural representations into the imported English language textbook:

It would be interesting and inviting for the students if we included cultures in Malaysia including the minorities, indigenous and other ethnics, as an initial step leading them to know more about international and global cultures and practices. Even though we're multicultural, we barely know or are aware of cultures other than our own. (P7)

I believe interculturality should not only surround Western practices. It should also be combined with local cultures and other circles of English. Even in the local context, there are many things, such as food and festivals that we're unaware of, especially in other races or ethnicities. I believe this is among other things that can be included in a textbook if interculturality is the primary concern in implementing the CEFR. (P10)

All of the participants acknowledged that IC can also be viewed from a micro perspective, where diverse local cultures should also be integrated as an initial step to introducing interculturality to young learners. P4 revealed that the previously used textbook that was locally developed covered the diversity in

the country, but later it was replaced by the imported book because the imported book was claimed to be aligned with the CEFR.

The majority of the participants emphasized (a) not only the need to include local cultural representation, (b) but also how the IC elements could be realized in this country of multiple races and ethnicities. In other words, the challenges lie in exploring how the existing IC elements in the textbook might be enriched for EFL teachers by making use of their local cultural resources.

5. Discussion

The findings reveal that teachers evaluated the *Super Minds* textbook to have ‘moderate’ authenticity. General attributes and the vocabulary of the textbook were rated with the highest mean scores compared to the rest of the elements. As for the physical attributes of the book, it is undeniably vibrant and has such qualities as interesting layout, effective use of texts and visuals; it is also complemented with ‘supplementary materials’—a criterion listed in the questionnaire. Such features, advocated by Tomlinson and Masuhara (2018), work as a strategy by commercial publishers to attract customers, albeit having no or little reference to English language teaching. As for the vocabulary, although the words used in the lessons are less applicable to the Malaysian setting, they may have met other criteria in the evaluation checklist—e.g., vocabulary lessons have achievable goals, vocabulary lessons are presented from simple to complex, vocabulary lessons are interesting to my students, and vocabulary lessons are adequate. The two elements, however, are still in the moderate category which may suggest that there is still room for improvement in making the content more authentic to local learners.

The lack of authenticity is due to the absence of local cultural representations in the content of the book. The book uses not only foreign comic characters—such as Misty, Whisper, Flash, and Thunder—which can raise confusion among learners regarding the characters’ ‘pronouns’ (cf. Leonard, 2024), but also illustrations that deviate from learners’ real-life situations. For instance, topics like “lunchtime” put forward western food that can be foreign to some learners in rural and remote areas. Such content presentations oppose ‘humanistic pedagogy’ (cf. Daftarifard & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011) considering learners’ immediate context and profiles in materials development (Tomlinson & Masuhara, 2018). The foreignness in the textbook content may create a gap between underprivileged learners, who have little exposure to the target language, and privileged learners at urban schools.

Learners’ demographic profiles undeniably played a part in their acceptance of the imported textbook. The findings from the interviews have highlighted that learners at indigenous schools could not cope with the textbook content as well as the activities in the textbook. As addressed by Renganathan (2021), rural

schools are the most affected by national education reforms because the challenges at the schools are of a different nature. Students are found to be less motivated, lack confidence, and fear to practice the language in classrooms. In this study, some remote and rural school teachers in the interviews raised the issue of 'illiteracy' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2008) that their students were facing. Therefore, a textbook with foreign content can be of a different level for their learners to deal with.

Despite having the privilege of adapting the materials that suits learners' needs, wants, and interests, there are backstories where materials adaptations are not always welcomed by education officers and school inspectors (Aziz et al., 2018). Regardless of the freedom to materials adaptations, teachers are overloaded with administrative work (Krishnan & Gan, 2022), hindering them from focusing on teaching and developing materials. Regarding teachers' power over the textbook content, R3's response is worth highlighting, where it was pointed out that the textbook should not be prescribed to teachers if they have to adapt or change the content completely. A textbook should provide teachers with teaching convenience that can facilitate their teaching, in this case, with minimal adaptation, so that it could save them preparation time for their classes.

Similar to authenticity, the IC element in the textbook was also rated as 'moderate' by the survey respondents. The main reason behind this is that the book was published by an international publisher, which is not necessarily meant for local learners. The concern with internationally published textbooks is that they are produced for profit and are detached from scholars' principles and recommendations (Dendrinis, 1992; Tomlinson, 2008, 2010). Due to mass production that aims for global distribution, local cultural representations are absent in the book. In this instance, the *Super Minds* textbook was available on the market, even before the curriculum was designed. Hence, the textbook development did not follow the standard principles of materials development that equally emphasize the need for the materials and the contextual appropriacy of the materials, in this case, learners' local settings.

As the national English language education is now aligned with the CEFR that promotes 'bilingual' and 'intercultural' education (Council of Europe, 2020; Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2015), diverse local cultures should also be considered in developing the textbook. Byram and Masuhara (2013) specify the need to acknowledge the culture of self and others at different levels—i.e., individual, community, and nation—in implementing intercultural education in language learning. It is apparent from the interview responses that all participants highlighted the need to include local cultures as a way to introduce interculturality to young learners. The *Super Minds* textbook is, therefore, seen as ineffective in executing CEFR principles in the national English language

curriculum because it is against the concept of interculturality promoted by the CEFR.

It is evident from the textbook evaluation that the book allows learners to discover foreign cultures and practices, but not their own, which contradicts the principle of intercultural competence (cf. Byram & Masuhara, 2013). At a lower primary school level, learners should be provided with opportunities to get to know their home cultures and the variations that constitute their society. From the differences within the society, learners can understand the historical and social backgrounds of their home country and should be able to find similarities in, and make comparisons with, the cultures of other countries as they grow up and move to higher education levels. Most importantly, learners can retain their own identity yet acknowledge others while learning a second or a foreign language.

It is time for materials developers to look at IC from a micro perspective, especially at the primary school level, where learners should be able to relate the materials content to their own existing knowledge. Based on prominent learning theories, such as cognitive constructivism (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016) and schema theories (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010), learners are mostly influenced by their individual experiences and prior knowledge to construct comprehension. In this case, the cultural presentations in the textbook are out of touch with learners' backgrounds, including the absence of local characters and settings in the illustrations that may further demotivate underprivileged learners with little exposure to the target language. It is recommended that a taste of local flavor be included in the English language textbook for the primary level to guide language learners to better understanding and relate to their daily practices. Local cultural representations included in the textbook could be a source of motivation and bring more relevance to learners to acquire the language as they could use the language to communicate about local events with other learners.

6. Conclusion

In sum, this study aimed at examining teachers' evaluation of the appropriacy of the *Super Minds* textbook in terms of 'authenticity' and 'IC'. In a mixed-methods approach engaging language teachers, a survey was administered to 450 English language teachers from across Malaysia, and 10 of these participants representing diverse school localities were also interviewed; results revealed that Malaysian teachers evaluated the *Super Minds* textbook as of moderate quality due to the absence of local illustrations and cultural representations, which made it difficult for some learners, especially those from lower socioeconomic strata of the society, to relate it to their daily practices. Data from the interviews, nonetheless, showed that some teachers

appreciated the complementary workbook and the audio materials that come with the textbook. Again, the complementary materials could only benefit privileged learners with wider exposure to the target language.

The teacher participants were all aware that the CEFR promotes bilingualism and IC. However, the *Super Minds* textbook is not the best tool for teaching interculturality in the second and foreign language contexts as it only encompasses western representations. Due to that, teachers raised their concerns about the need to view interculturality from a micro perspective. The previously used textbook, locally developed by local experts, was believed to prepare learners with better intercultural competence as it covers local and foreign cultural representations. Since the CEFR does not limit, nor specify, any contexts to be included in teaching material, it is time to have wider local cultural representations in English textbooks to instill intercultural competence in second and foreign-language learners. After all, not everything produced by international publishers can satisfy local learners' needs and interests.

This study emphasizes the need to consider teachers' voices from all school localities in textbook evaluation. It is believed that the imported textbook can only accommodate learners with prior knowledge of the subjects presented in the book—such as foreign places, festivals, and foods, but not underprivileged learners. Future textbook development must consider learners' profiles from diverse backgrounds and language proficiency levels. The current textbook practice seems to emulate the one-size-fits-all model, where learners with low proficiency have to bear the consequences of the textbook policy that could affect their motivation to learn the language. It also must be highlighted that school teachers can only practice materials adaptation if their non-teaching workload is reduced. Materials adaptations must also be allowed and acknowledged by all top levels, ranging from the Ministry to education officers and school inspectors.

This study, however, is limited to the Malaysian context, where English is proclaimed as a second language (ESL). Even so, the language is still treated as foreign in some school localities, especially in rural and remote areas. Learning English with foreign content could be too much for them to handle; academically, therefore, the acceptance of using an imported textbook with foreign cultural representations could not be maximized. The result might be different in other ASEAN countries, like Singapore, that have more acceptance towards foreign cultures, and it could be the opposite in countries like Thailand, Cambodia, and Indonesia, where English is a foreign language (EFL). A comparative study involving countries with different types of textbooks, local and imported, is highly recommended as it can be beneficial to materials developers and policymakers in the region.

Authors' Statement

All authors declare that they have discussed and conceived this paper together. The first author initiated the idea and collected the data, while the second and third authors contributed to the whole conception, editing and improving the draft.

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